

the 9:7 ratio with a X^2 value of 2.29, nonsignificant at 1% level. Results confirmed the hypothesis that the height variability of the cross results from digenic segregation with complementary gene effects because each parent has one

of the dominant genes. Segregates had from early to medium growth duration and there was no obvious association between plant height and growth duration.

The shortest plants in the segregating

population were much shorter than the shortest parent and are double recessives, making them of great significance as representatives of a new source of dwarfing obtained by combining two recessive genes. □

Ratoon performance of some short-duration rice cultures

K. Karunakaran, M. B. Jalajakumari, and P. Sreedevi, Regional Agricultural Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala, India

Twenty rice varieties constituting the ninth International Rice Yield Nursery

(early) were grown in three replications at Pattambi during the 1981 kharif. Seedlings were transplanted at 15 cm × 10 cm spacing and received 70-35-35 kg NPK/ha. The main crop was harvested to leave 15-cm-tall stubble and entries were assessed for ratoon performance. The ratoon crop was not fertilized or sprayed.

It was not irrigated but 625 mm of rain fell over 38 rainy days.

Varietal differences in the ratoon yields were significant. Five IRRI lines—IR9209-48-3-2, IR9761-19-1, IR13427-40-2-3-3, IR13429-109-2-2-1, and IR13429-287-3—were promising (see table). □

Main crop and ratoon performance of some rice varieties at Pattambi, India.

Variety	Duration (days)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop
BAU2-3-43	108	56	3.2	0.1
BKN7033-13-1-1-3-2	108	56	3.8	0.2
BPT1235	110	54	4.4	0.1
BR109-74-2-2-2	119	45	3.7	0.2
BR161-2B-58	117	47	3.5	0.2
Chianung Sen yu 13	113	51	3.6	0.4
IR9209-48-3-2	104	60	4.9	0.3
IR9761-19-1	103	61	4.9	0.3
IR9828-91-2-3	108	56	4.0	0.1
IR13427-40-2-3-3	113	51	4.6	0.5
IR13427-60-1-3-2-2	103	61	4.8	0.2
IR13429-109-2-2-1	108	56	4.6	0.4
IR13429-196-1	108	56	4.9	0.2
IR13429-287-3	113	51	4.8	0.3
MRC603-303	109	55	3.7	0.2
MTU34 19	116	48	3.6	0.0
Taichung Sen Yu 285	113	51	3.6	0.4
TNAU1756	103	61	3.8	0.1
IR36	108	56	4.2	0.2
KAU23332-2	113	51	4.5	0.1
CD ($P=0.05$)	—	—	0.55	0.21

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Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Promising TKM6 rice mutants

S. R. Sree Rangasamy and C. R. Anandakumar, School of Genetics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

TKM6 (GEB24/Co 18 hybrid derivative) mutants were isolated after gamma irradiation and treatment with chemical mutagens ethyl methane sulfonate (EMS)

and di-ethyl sulfate (DES) either singly or in combination. Several dwarf mutants were isolated from the different treatments in M2 generation. Among them, three dwarf macromutants were identified as promising and grown through M3 and M4 (see table).

The dwarf mutant obtained with a 30 kR gamma ray dose was early maturing and had reduced leaf area, grain size,

and total dry matter production, but higher per day production, chlorophyll content, number of grains per panicle, and harvest index. The mutant obtained by combining treatments of 35 kR gamma rays + 30 mM EMS had greater leaf area, chlorophyll content, and per day productivity than the control. The third mutant, obtained with a 35 kR gamma ray dose, yielded higher than the

control because of increased leaf area, chlorophyll content, and grains/panicle, and had slender grains. Growth duration,

however, was 10 days longer.

The mutants were photosynthetically efficient and the induced dwarfism in

these mutants increased yields. They are being tested for direct use and as parents to provide alternative dwarfing sources. □

Performance of TKM6 and its mutants for different traits. ^a

Mutants	Duration (days)	Height (cm)	Productive tillers (no.)	Leaf area (cm ²)	Chlorophyll (mg/g)		Grains per panicle	Length-breadth ratio of grain	Productivity per day (kg/ha)	Total dry matter productivity/plant (g)	Harvest index
					'a'	'b'					
TKM6 control	120	120.0	8	17.89	0.715	0.328	110	3.00	37.50	30.0	30.00
TKM6 30 kR D ₁	110	70.0 (-41.6)	7	14.49 (-19.0)	1.009 (+41.0)	0.586 (+78.8)	145 (+31.8)	1.73	45.45 (+21.20)	17.95 (-40.16)	55.71
TKM6 35 + 30	120	116.0 (-5)	11	21.73 (+21.4)	1.043 (+45.8)	0.480 (+46.2)	135 (+22.7)	3.40	58.33 (+55.54)	41.00 (+36.66)	34.15
TKM6 35 kR D ₃	130	75.0 (-37.5)	10	19.14 (+ 6.9)	1.006 (+40.5)	0.597 (+82.0)	165 (+50.0)	3.30	61.54 (+64.08)	37.50 (+25.0)	42.67

^aFigures in parentheses indicate percentage increase or decrease over control.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Inheritance of blast *Pyricularia oryzae* resistance in rice.

J. A. Flores-Gaxiola, director, Papaloapan Experiment Station, Veracruz, Mexico, and F. L. Nuque, assistant scientist, Plant Pathology Department; J. P. Crill, former head of the Plant Pathology Department; and G. S. Khush, head of the Plant Breeding Department, IRRI

We sought to determine the number of leaf blast resistance genes present in some rice breeding lines and varieties, based on the presence or absence of lesions on F₁ and F₂ populations. The F₁s and segregating populations were inoculated with several races of the pathogen by injection. This study was conducted at IRRI in 1979 and 1980.

Lines derived from Tetep/IR8 (IR1905-81-3-1, IR3259-PP5-160-1, and IR3259-PP8-172-7) were resistant to six blast isolates and the Taiwanese variety Pai-kan-tao was resistant to three (see table). None of the varieties were resistant to an isolate from large lesions on Tetep. IR442-2-58, IR8, Peta, and Nongbaek were susceptible to all seven isolates. Among parents resistant to the same isolate, different genes controlled resistance. Also, for a given parent, dif-

Number of genes resistant to specific isolates of the blast fungus, identified in three breeding lines and one variety.

Line, variety	Fungus race	Resistance genes (no.)	Gene interaction
IR1905-81-3-la	IB45	2	Complementary
	ID-15	2	Complementary
	ID-16	1	Dominant
	IH-1(43+PO7-10) ^b	1+1	Dominant
	II-1	1	Dominant
IR3259-PP5-160-1 ^a	IB-45	2	Complementary
	ID-15	2	Complementary
	ID-16	1	Dominant
	IH-1(43+PO7-10) ^b	1+1	Dominant
	II-1	1	Dominant
IR3259-PP8-172-7 ^c	IB-45	2	Complementary
	ID-15	2	Complementary
	ID-16	2	Complementary
	IH-1 (43+PO7-10) ^b	1+1	Dominant
	II-1	1	Dominant
Pai-kan-tao ^d	IH-1 (43+PO7-10) ^b	2+2	Complementary
	II-1	2	Duplicate

^a In this line, the genes resistant to the races studied appear to be the same or allelic. ^b Isolates 43 and PO7-10 were differentiated as race IH-1 but distinct genes controlled resistance to each of them.

^c The resistance genes in this line are apparently the same or allelic to those in IR905-81-3-1 and IR3259-PP5-160-1 except for race ID-16. ^d Genes for resistance detected in this variety were non-allelic to the corresponding genes in IR905-81-3-1, IR3259-PP5-160-1, and IR3259-PP8-172-7.

ferent genes controlled resistance to different races.

Apparently, several blast resistance genes are available in a single genotype. Different genes control resistance to a particular race in different genotypes—

the genes in Pai-kan-tao that govern resistance to race IH-1 (isolates PO7-10 and 43) and II-1 are different from those in IR81905-81-3-1, IR3259-PP5-160-1, and IR3259-PP8-172-7. No complementary recessive genes for resistance were